

Mixed-ligand Cobalt(III) Complexes involving Non-basic Schiff Bases

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Mixed-ligand complexes of cobalt(III) involving Schiff bases of different basicity have been studied in some details¹. In order to investigate the possible formation of cobalt(III) mixed-ligand complexes involving neutral Schiff bases, some reactions have been carried out with the Schiff bases derived from benzaldehyde and the diamines.

Results and Discussion

Schiff bases derived from benzaldehyde and either ethylenediamine (BZEN), 1,3-diaminopropane (BZPN_x) or 1,2-diaminopropane (BZPN_y) could not be isolated in the solid state.

Attempts to isolate the complexes (prepared in situ) in solid state introducing suitable anions (e.g. ClO₄⁻) were not possible. The complex solutions were then treated with ethylenediamine (En) and the mixtures were subjected to aerial oxidation prior to reflux.

The dark-brown coloured solutions containing the cobalt(III) complexes were treated sodium cobaltinitrite dissolved in minimum volume of water. On filtration, Na[Co(En)(NO₂)₄] (1) was obtained as reddish brown residue and the filtrate yielded [Co(BZDN)₂(En)] [Co(NO₂)₆] (2–4). Attempts to isolate these compounds as perchlorate or tetrafluoroborate salts in the solid state were unsuccessful.

Compound 1 is insoluble in water, alcohol and other common organic solvents. Compounds 2–4 are moderately soluble in water, sparingly soluble in alcohol but insoluble in other common organic solvents. All of them are, however, soluble in DMF, DMSO and pyridine. All the compounds are either diamagnetic or slightly paramagnetic.

Infrared spectra of various Schiff bases and their transition metal complexes have been extensively studied², and the results are applicable in the present complexes also. Important ir bands in KBr phase of the present complexes are given in Table 1. The ν_{O-N} frequencies appear at 1595–1605 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of coordinated ketimine groups. A little broadening of the bands may be attributed to the presence of C=C, C–C, NH₂ and NO₂ stretching modes which also complicated their separate assignments. The medium but sharp band at ~840 cm⁻¹ assignable to NO₂ bending vibrations, supports the presence of N-bonded NO₂ groups in the present mixed-ligand chelates³.

The electronic spectra (Table 1) of the compounds show three bands at 28 000–25 000, 23 000–20 000 and 18 000–16 000 cm⁻¹ and may be considered very typical for pseudo-octahedral complexes of cobalt(III)⁴. The first band may be assigned due to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transition mixed up possibly with the metal to ligand (*t*_{2g} → π*) transition, and the other two bands as due to the split components of ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_g transition.

Experimental

Elemental analyses were performed by conventional methods. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (nujol/water) on a Cary 14 spectrophotometer.

Preparation of complexes: Benzaldehyde (2.12 g, 20 mmol) diluted with ethanol (20 ml) was added to ethylenediamine (0.54 g, 9 mmol) or 1,3-diaminopropane (0.67 g, 9 mmol) or 1,2-diaminopropane (0.67 g, 9 mmol) diluted with ethanol (20 ml) and

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC AND IR SPECTRAL DATA COMPLEXES (1–4)

Compd. no.	Compd.	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹)
1	Na[Co(En)(NO ₂) ₄]	^a 26 426, 23 928, 18 110sh, 15 980	3 290–3 230, 1 565, 1 460, 1 365, 1 328, 1 255, 1 165, 1 060, 964, 840, 745, 710
2	[Co(BZEN) ₂ (En)][Co(NO ₂) ₆]	^b 40 224, 27 122, 20 100sh, 16 420	3 290–3 260, 1 598, 1 465, 1 375, 1 362, 1 325, 1 280, 830, 720, 665
3	[Co(BZPN _x) ₂ (En)][Co(NO ₂) ₆]	^b 41 000, 26 728, 19 500, 16 728	3 280–3 240, 1 605, 1 460, 1 365, 1 336, 1 290, 838, 730, 678
4	[Co(BZPN _y) ₂ (En)][Co(NO ₂) ₆]	^b 39 890, 27 727, 21 565, 17 355	—

^aIn nujol, ^bIn water. Extractions are not calculated due to moderate solubility.

refluxed for 1 h. Cobalt acetate tetrahydrate (1.84 g, 9 mmol) was then added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The resulting brown solution was cooled to room temperature and on treatment with ethylenediamine (0.54 g, 9 mmol) was subjected to aerial oxidation for 3 h and finally refluxed for 2 h. The dark brown solution so obtained was reduced to half and to it was added sodium cobaltinitrite (3.02 g, 9 mmol) dissolved in water (~5 ml). An immediate precipitation took place and the mixture was warmed on a water-bath for 10 min and filtered. $\text{Na}[\text{Co}(\text{En})(\text{NO}_2)_4]$ (1) was isolated as brown solid, m.p. $\sim 50-55^\circ\text{d}$ (Found: C, 6.99; H, 2.67; N, 26.10; Co, 18.29. Calcd. for: C, 7.36; H, 2.45; N, 25.77; Co, 18.09%). The filtrate on reduction of volume and subsequent cooling yielded dark-brown $[\text{Co}(\text{BZEN})_2(\text{En})][\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ (2), m.p. $270-75^\circ\text{d}$ (Found: C, 44.65; H, 4.12; N, 17.79; Co, 12.54. Calcd. for: C, 44.06; H, 4.32; N, 18.14; Co, 12.74%); dark-red $[\text{Co}(\text{BZPN}_x)_2(\text{En})][\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ (3), m.p. $\sim 300^\circ\text{d}$ (Found: C, 45.21; H, 4.68; N, 18.10; Co, 12.05. Calcd. for: C, 44.68; H, 4.47; N, 17.87; Co, 12.55%); dark-red

$[\text{Co}(\text{BZPN}_y)_2(\text{En})][\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ (4), m.p. $\sim 300^\circ\text{d}$; (Found: C, 44.96; H, 4.31; N, 18.20; Co, 12.10; Calcd. for: C, 44.68; H, 4.47; N, 17.87; Co, 12.55%).

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